

Management of Kampavata Through Panchakarma-A Case Report

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ABSTRACT: *Kampavata* is a *Vata Pradhana Roga* where there will be a *Kampa* (tremor) as a main *lakshana* and may associated with *Sthambha*, *Vinamana*, *Gurugatrata* etc. The *lakshanas* of *Kampavata* are similar to the clinical features of Parkinson's disease which is a neurodegenerative disorder that affects movement, balance and coordination. It can significantly impact a person's quality of life causing various motor and non-motor symptoms. The aim of this case study is to provide the quality life to the patient suffering from *Kampavata* through effective *Panchakarma* treatment. *Vangasena Samhita* introduced the concept of treating *Kampavata* for the first time like *Abhyanga*, *Sweda*, *Nasya*, *Niruha*, *Anuvasana*, *Virechana* and *Shirobasti* are said to be beneficial remedies¹.

KEY WORDS: *Kampavata*, Parkinson's disease, *Shirobasti*, *Abhyanga*

INTRODUCTION

In Charaka Samhita *Kampavata* is found by the name *Vepathu*². It has been included in the 80 *Vataja Nanatmaja Vyadhi*. The word *Kampavata* is formed by the union of two words *Kampa* and *Vata*. The word *Kampa* means "to move" or "to shake". Hence, the word *Kampavata* means the disorders of *Vata* which is not in *Samadoshavastha* and it is characterized by *Kampa*. As its a *Vataja Roga*, So, the causative factors which provoke *Vata* can be considered as the etiological factor.

Basavarajeeyam has described and explained the symptoms of *Kampavata* which resembles with the symptoms of Parkinson's disease. In modern, Parkinson's disease is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder. The Lakshanas like *Karapadatale Kampa* (tremor in hands and feet), *Dehabhramana* (Romberg's), *Nidrabhanga* (Disturbed sleep), *Matiksheena*(dementia), certain symptoms like *Sthambha* (Rigidity), *Chestahani*(Slowness of movement), *Vinamana* (Flexed Posture), *Vakvikriti*(Speech disorders) are also grouped under the features of *Kampavata*³. In modern science other than above mentioned symptoms, they have described as Rigidity, Bradykinesia, Monotonous speech, Postural instability, Depression, Hallucinations, Dementia, Nocturia, Constipation. In essence, while *Kampavata* in Ayurveda and Parkinson's disease in modern medicine share many symptom similarities, they are viewed and treated from different perspectives based on their understanding of the underlying causes and mechanisms of disease. The present case study is to emphasize on the management of *Kampavata* through *Panchakarma* effectively.

Active range of motion: (AROM)	Upper extremity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited shoulder flexion in right and left shoulder
	Lower extremity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small limitation with hip flexion
Passive range of motion: (PROM)	Upper extremity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited shoulder flexion in right and left shoulder
	Lower extremity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small limitation with hip flexion
Manual Muscle Testing (MMT)	Upper extremity strength	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 3/5
	Lower extremity strength	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 3/5
Neurological Examination		
Tone	Rigidity is present on both sides of the body	
Reflexes	Exaggerated	

Investigations:

MRI – BRAIN (20/04//2024)

Impression: Normal MRI appearance of the neuroparenchyma noted on MRI sequence.

Table no. 2 Showing the Panchakarma Treatment

Date	Treatment	Medicine
28/02/2025 to 02/03/2025	<i>Sarvanga Mridu Udvartana</i>	<i>Kolakulattadi Choorna</i>
	<i>Sarvanga Parisheka</i>	<i>Dashamoola Kashaya</i>
	<i>Choorna Basti</i>	<i>Hingwasthaka Choorna</i>
03/03/2025 to 06/03/2025	<i>Shirodhara</i>	<i>Sahacharadi Taila</i>
	<i>Sarvanga Abhyanga</i>	<i>Mahanarayana Taila</i>
	<i>Sarvanga Parisheka</i>	<i>Dashamoola Kashaya</i>
	<i>Matra Basti</i>	<i>Sahacharadi Taila (60ml)</i>
07/03/2025 to 27/03/2025	<i>Shirobasti</i>	<i>Sahacharadi Taila</i>
	<i>Sarvanga Abhyanga</i>	<i>Mahanarayana Taila</i>
	<i>Sarvanga Parisheka</i>	<i>Dashamoola Kashaya</i>
	<i>Matra Basti</i>	<i>Sahacharadi Taila (60ml)</i>

Table no. 3 Showing the Shamanoushadhi

Sl. No	Shamanoushadhi	Dosage
1.	<i>Dhanadanayanadi Kashaya</i>	15ml/BD/BF with Warm Water
2.	<i>Tab Brihat Vata Chintamani</i>	1BD/AF
3.	<i>Tab Sumanas</i>	1BD/AF

DISCUSSION

Sarvanga Mridu Udvartana with *Kolakulattadi Choorna* is *Kapha -Vatahara* and *Shonitam Krichramapi* which helps in *Amapachana* and attaining *Srotovishodhana* with proper circulation and reduces stiffness. *Sarvanga Parisheka* with *Dashamaoola Kashaya* acts as a *Vatahara*, *Rujahara*, *Brihmana*⁴. It acts as vasodilator and improves circulation. Hence, it is very beneficial in conditions like *Sthambha* and *Sankocha*. It cures *Sthambha* and *Guruta*. In *Kampavata*, it acts on *Sheeta* and *Guru Guna* of *Kapha* and *Vata* producing *Sthambha*.

Abhyanga with *Mahanarayana Taila* brings *Snehana*⁵ effect along with the action of *Vatahara*, *Brihmana*. As *Abhyanga* has a *Snigdha*, *Guru*, and *Mridu* properties. In *Kampavata*, it acts on *Laghu Guna* and *Chala Guna* and it also does the *Balavardhana*, *Agnivardhana* and nourishes the *Shushka Dhatu*.

Shirodhara and *Shirobasti* are indicated in *Kampavata*. According to Acharya Vagbhata, *Murdhini Taila* is highly beneficial for brain, nerves, sense organs and it controls vitiated *Vayu* and *Pitta* in the head⁶. *Shirobasti* and *Shirodhara* nourishes the nervous system, improves cognitive function and reduces stress and anxiety.

Initially, as the patient has an involuntary movement of head the *Shirodhara* procedure is planned. Later days when the movement of head reduced *Shirobasti* is adapted as a treatment along with *Abhyanga* and *Matra Basti*. *Sahacharadi Taila* which is mentioned by *Vangasena* used for both *Shirobasti*, and *Matra Basti*⁷. *Shirobasti* helped the patient to overcome from sleep disturbance and also provided the calmness of mind.

Matra Basti with *Sahacharadi Taila*, as it is indicated in *Vata* related neurological disorders by its *Snigdha*, *Guru* and *Ushna* properties alleviate *Ruksha*, *Laghu* and *Sheeta Guna* of *Vata* which helps in pacification of *Vata Dosha* and beneficial in neurological disorders like *Kampavata* works as a nourishing remedy that supports overall vitality and health.

Dhanadanayanadi Kashaya used in treatment of tremors of various neurological etiology, such as shaking of hands, legs or head, restores the nerve function and to soothe exacerbated *Vata Dosha* in case of *Kampavata*. *Brihat Vata Chintamani Rasa* is having *Medhya*, *Rasayana*, *Balya*, *Kshayagna*, *Ojovardhaka* property hence it was prescribed in *Kampavata*. Tablet *Sumanas* as it contains *Brahmi*, *Shankhapushpi*,

Jatamamsi, Sarpagandha, Parasika Yavani and *Vacha* which helps in reducing anxiety, emotional distress and also provides mild tranquilizing effect.

During the treatment period the patient had a lightness in the body. Later as the treatment proceeds, he had a reduced tremor, rigidity in limbs. The Exertional dyspnea was reduced and able to get up without much difficulty and he was able to walk without fall with minimum stiffness and the pain in low back got reduced. He was able to sleep without any disturbance. There was an improvement in speech and gait.

After follow up he had a relief from stiffness, pain, dysarthria, Exertional dyspnea, and the tremors got reduced effectively.

CONCLUSION

Kampavata is a *Vata Pradhana Roga*. The management of the disease by *Vata* and *Kaphahara chikitsa* with *Panchakarma* like *Shirobasti, Abhyanga, Parisheka* and *Matra basti* helps in managing the *Kampavata Lakshanas* and enhancing the quality of life including physical therapy and lifestyle modifications makes the patient to lead his life without much difficulties. Further clinical research is required to substantiate the effectiveness of Ayurvedic treatments for *Kampavata*.

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